

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART VII DETERMINATION OF AROMATIC COMPOUNDS WITH POTASSIUM CHLORATE.

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Phenol, *p*-nitroaniline, diphenylamine and quinone have been determined at 25° by titrating them potentiometrically against standard potassium chlorate in presence of hydrochloric acid, using platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode.

The potentiometric method for the detection of the end-point in the titration of aromatic compounds with bromate in the presence of bromide, has been applied by Callan and Horrobin (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, **47**, 334). No attempt has been made to study potentiometrically the chlorination of the organic compounds with suitable reagents.

In the present investigation, phenol, *p* nitroaniline, diphenylamine and quinone have been chlorinated by a solution of potassium chlorate in presence of hydrochloric acid.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

A known weight of the organic compounds was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was titrated potentiometrically against standard potassium chlorate at 25°, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The titrant was added very slowly from a burette and the mixture was kept thoroughly stirred by a mechanical stirrer.

Phenol, *p*-nitroaniline, diphenylamine and quinone were quantitatively converted into trichlorophenol (m.p. 68°), dichloronitroaniline (m. p. 189°), tetrachlorodiphenylamine (m. p. 133°) and tetrachloroquinone (m. p. 290° in a sealed tube) respectively.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration, as typical of that set, is recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

Titration of 0.0268 g. of quinone dissolved in 20 c. c. of water and 40 c. c. of conc. HCl against $M/60\text{-KClO}_3$.

KClO ₃ .	E. M. F.	E/C (m. volts/c.c.).	KClO ₃ .	E. M. F.	E/C (m. volts/c.c.).
0.000 c. c.	0.410 volts		19.850 c.c.	0.580 volts	
		50			—
1.000	0.460		19.900	0.580	
		10			—
5.000	0.500		19.950	0.580	
		8			—
10.000	0.540		20.000	0.580	
		8			—
15.000	0.580		20.050	0.580	
		—			—
18.000	0.580		20.100	0.580	
		—			2200
18.500	0.580		20.150	0.690	(maximum)
		—			1200
18.800	0.580		20.200	0.750	
		—			1000
19.000	0.580		20.250	0.800	
		—			400
19.200	0.580		20.350	0.840	
		—			107
19.400	0.580		20.650	0.872	
		—			44
19.600	0.580		21.150	0.894	
		—			26
19.800	0.580		22.150	0.920	
		—			

DISCUSSION.

In these titrations, the E. M. F. rose on the first few additions of the titrant. On further addition of titrant, the potential remained constant till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point, there was a sharp jump in potential followed by a steady rise.

From the volume of potassium chlorate solution required in each titration, corresponding to the equivalence point, the amount of each compound was calculated. In the following table the values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substance taken.

TABLE II.

P h e n o l		<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline		Diphenylamine		Q u i n o n e	
taken.	found.	taken.	found.	taken.	found.	taken.	(found.
0.2121 g.	0.2118 g.	0.3104 g.	0.3098 g.	0.1904 g.	0.1901 g.	0.1213 g.	0.1216 g
0.1275	0.1271	0.1728	0.1725	0.1271	0.1267	0.0806	0.0810
0.0568	0.0565	0.1554	0.1551	0.0955	0.0952	0.0604	0.0608
0.0426	0.0423	0.1035	0.1032	0.0644	0.0640	0.0402	0.0406
0.0356	0.0352	0.0595	0.0591	0.0425	0.0423	0.0268	0.0271

The results show that phenol, *p*-nitroaniline, diphenylamine and quinone can be potentiometrically determined by using standard potassium chlorate, in presence of hydrochloric acid.

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